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IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF MEASURING SOCIAL CAPITAL IN INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the analytical approaches and capabilities of empirical measurement of social capital.. It presents a new understanding of the concept of social capital, an original methodology of measurement that allows us to assess the level of social capital in an international company. Based on the empirical data obtained from the research, it is possible to diagnose and monitor social capital.

Keywords: Social Capital, Trust, Social Networks, Organizational Culture, Social Capital Configuration, Measurement Methodology.

Introduction

Social capital is a complex of human relationships that undergoes conversion into other forms of capital. The existence of such capital in an international company helps to increase the efficiency of its activities. Similar processes take place at the social level - in society itself. A society that has a stock of social capital is more successful in economic development, while people are healthier and happier [Almedom, 2005]. Social capital meets the characteristics of economic capital, such as: limitation, ability to accumulate, liquidity, conversion and ability of transfer. The ability to accumulate social capital is not an individual characteristic, but rather the specificity of the network in which individuals are involved [Shengelia, 2017]. Nowadays, the impact of social capital on the economy has been

proven in a number of studies [Shengelia, 2017] They usually establish the connection between social capital (primarily trust) and economic indicators. This reveals the high role of the confidence factor in economic development, but does not fully explain the impact of social capital on business relationships. Cross-cultural comparisons of social capital have become an important factor in business development [Fukuyama, 1999].

It is clear that the mechanism of impact of social capital on the business is impossible without perfecting its research methods. A special place in the study of social capital is occupied by transnational companies (TNCs), which are distinguished by their specifics and features. In this context, it is important to improve the

quality of internal integration, coordination and exchange of resources between TNK and its branches. Studies have shown that they are often not focused on increasing the efficiency of these companies (Burt, 2007.).

According to scientists, it is important to use social capital to build trust between TNC headquarters and branches (Kostova., Roth. 2003). The concept of social capital is important in the process of developing new personnel strategies for TNCs. Without understanding how social networks work in different countries, it is difficult to make the right personnel decisions. (Adler, Kwon. 2002). In the process of measuring social capital at the international company level, it is important to determine who enjoys the right to use social capital - an individual or an organization; The answer to this question is ambiguous. On the one hand, the social capital of an organization cannot exist without its carrier-individuals. It is clear that if all its employees leave the organization, the social capital will also disappear [Knoke, 1999]. On the other hand, the social capital of the organization, even though it consists of the individual social capital of the employees, belongs to the organization as a whole and is reflected in the good reputation of the company in the market.

The social capital of an international company as Research category

Empirical measurement of social capital faces two serious problems. These are:

1. The eclectic nature of this concept;
2. Its multifaceted impact on the organization.

Consider each of them: Social capital is an eclectic concept that is difficult to operate at the level of a particular organization. As a research category, social capital is a complex technical construction and it consists of three interrelated components: Trust, social interaction (networks), norms and rules (culture). In the organizational

environment, all three components are closely related, although in the process of measuring social capital, it is usually reduced to the analysis of one of its components - trust, networks or organizational culture. Therefore, the methodology of measuring social capital faces the problem of considering all three of its components.

In contrast to existing methods of measuring individual aspects of social capital, presented in the approach, All three aspects of social capital are considered, reflecting the state and quality of social relations according to all three parameters.

Social Capital Research Methodology in an International Company

The international company "Integration Point Georgia" was selected by us as the object of research. A standardized questionnaire was used to measure social capital. It reflected three main blocks - trust, interaction, internalized normality, as well as information about the respondent's personal characteristics. For each component of social capital, a set of questionnaires was developed in a polar judgment format in which respondents were asked to rate on a quantitative scale. The scale is deliberately designed to contain no positive or negative scores to avoid the normative nature of the assessment. The main task is to assess the real situation. The assessment of the social capital components of TNCs is carried out at different levels: Divisions, the company as a whole and the group. As the pilot study showed, ordinary employees have a poor understanding of the situation at the company group level; We therefore used two types of questionnaires - one for managers and one for employees. Employees value social capital components at the level of their departments and company, while managers value the company and group level. Levels of Social Capital (SC) assessments by groups of respondents are presented in Table № 1 (see Table № 1)

Table №1

Levels of Social Capital (SC) assessment by groups of respondents

Level of interaction	Departments	Company	Group
Employees	SC assessment at department level	SC assessment at company level	
Managers		SC assessment at company level	SC assessment at group level

Thus, at the company level, social capital is valued by both ordinary employees and managers. Only employees are valued at the department level and only managers at the company group level. The questions for employees and managers are identical, that allows us to evaluate social capital by all employees of the company. In general, the characteristics of social capital at each level can be assessed according to three parameters: the level, strength and effect of social capital, which are determined by the nature of its impact on internal organizational integration. The level of social capital is determined on the basis of the coefficients calculated from the data obtained, which give a clear, generalized picture of its structure in different departments and in the company as a whole. The following social capital ratios are used in the analysis:

1. Integral Ratio of Social Capital (IR)
2. General ratios of social capital:
 - Confidence coefficient (CC),
 - Interaction openness coefficient (OC),
 - Internalized normality coefficient (INC).
3. Private Ratios (PR):
 - Trust-competence (TC),
 - Trust-decency (TD), trust-care (TC),
 - Vertical confidence (VC);
 - Awareness (AR),
 - Cooperation (CR), etc.

For the interpretation of the integral coefficient of social capital, as well as the general coefficients characteristic of its individual components, it is more informative and correct to use a comparative perspective. For this purpose, the dynamics of changes in coefficients over time are taken into account. The toolkit uses

statistical analysis methods such as: calculating correlation coefficients (determining two-way relationships using Pearson's R). The score is calculated according to the weighted average indicators (option "Average" in SPSS program).

The strength / weakness (volatility) of social capital is determined by the horizontal configuration harmony indicator, by determining the contribution of various components of social capital to its general level.

The general level of social capital is assessed as an integrative factor of the workforce based on the calculation of the integral coefficients of social capital at the department, company and group level. Integral ratios of

social capital give the whole organization an idea of its level, positive or negative. In our study, the total integral ratio of social capital for the company is 0.34 (see Table №2), Which indicates the high level of social capital of the entire organization. At the same time, the analysis of the structure of social capital shows its quite significant inconsistencies at different levels. The highest score is at the level of subdivisions (0.48), At the company level (0.31), at the group level (0.12). We can assume that it is the level of departments that is currently the main resource of the company's social capital.

Table № 2

	Subdivisions	Company	Group	General (IR)
Employees	0,48	0,39	-	0,43
Managers	-	0,31	0,14	0,23
Integral ratios of social capital	0,46	0,31	0,12	0,34

The analysis of integral coefficients at different levels As well makes it possible to judge the "vertical" harmony of social capital. The smaller the difference between the levels of the various coefficients, the more harmonious the social capital and the stronger its integrative function. The high degree of dispersion of ratios makes it possible to identify the most problematic levels of social capital formation. As can be seen from Table. 2, this is the group level in a given company. The importance of the integral coefficient at this level is found in the zone "unstable", ie a significant part of the respondents negatively assess the relations at the level of the group of companies. As can be seen from Table. 2, this is the group level in a given company. The importance of the integral coefficient at this level is found in the zone "unstable", ie a significant part of the respondents negatively assess the relations at the level of the group of companies.

Comparison of integral ratios of different categories of staff (employees and managers) shows higher organizational integration of ordinary employees (0.43; 0.23) compared to managers. At the same time, it is relatively close for ordinary employees and managers to assess the situation at the company level (although managers have a relatively negative perception (0.31; 0.39). The reason for the more critical attitude of managers is a better understanding of the situation in the company.

Judging by the integral ratios of social capital, both at the company and group level, managers have a weaker impact on social capital than other employees, which suggests that the methodology used in the area of involvement of company managers has made it possible to identify problem areas.

To understand how a company's integral social capital is formed, why it increases or decreases, it is necessary to consider the structure of social capital and, above all, its level in identical companies, which is the subject of independent research.

It should be noted that the absolute values of the level of social capital are difficult to interpret, so the main focus was on the possibilities of comparative

analysis of the obtained coefficients. Comparing the situation in different departments and groups makes it possible to identify problem areas, while periodic monitoring of social capital allows us to observe the current changes in the dynamics in this area.

Conclusion

Social capital is a complex methodological category and it includes three interrelated components: trust; Social interaction (networks); Norms and rules (culture). All three of these components are closely related, although the analysis of trust, networks, or organizational culture is used separately in the process of measuring social capital. Therefore, the existing methodology for measuring social capital does not allow measuring all three components.

Unlike existing methods of social capital, in our approach, it is possible to consider all three aspects of social capital, thus achieving a reflection of all three parameters of the state and quality of social relations.

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ВПЛИВ ДЕМОКРАТИЗАЦІЇ ВІТЧИЗНЯНОЇ ВИБОРЧОЇ СИСТЕМИ НА СТРИМАННЯ ЕМІГРАЦІЙНИХ НАСТРОЇВ РОБОЧОЇ СИЛИ

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THE INFLUENCE OF DEMOCRATIZATION OF THE DOMESTIC ELECTORAL SYSTEM ON RESTRAINT OF EMIGRATION MOOD OF THE LABOR FORCE

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АНОТАЦІЯ

У статті розглядаються тенденції розвитку еміграції робочої сили з України. Зокрема, з міської та сільської місцевості. Основна увага звернута на дослідження впливу демократизації вітчизняної виборчої системи на стримання еміграційних настроїв активної працездатної частки робочої сили нашої держави. Запропонована модель демократичної виборчої технології, провадження якої сприятиме формуванню депутатського корпусу об'єктивної народної довіри, яка зорієнтована та очікує їх реальних дій, у тому числі і у напрямку забезпечення належних умов праці населення України на рівні світових стандартів.

ABSTRACT

The article examines the development trends of labor force emigration from Ukraine. In particular, from urban and rural areas. The main attention is paid to the study of the influence of the democratization of the national electoral system on the restraint of emigration attitudes of the active working part of the labor force of our country. The proposed model of democratic election technology, the implementation of which will contribute to the formation of the deputy corps of objective public trust, which is oriented and expects their real actions, including in the direction of ensuring proper working conditions of the population of Ukraine at the level of world standards.